

Oxidimetric determination of some common reductants with 1-chlorobenzimidazole in aqueous acetic acid medium

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Abstract : This present investigation deals with the utility of 1-chlorobenzimidazole (CBI) as an oxidimetric titrant in the potentiometric determination of some common reductants in aqueous acetic acid medium.

Keywords : CBI, reductants, oxidimetric titration.

Introduction

A few N-halo compounds such as N-chlorosuccinimide (NCS)¹, N-chlorosaccharin (NCSA)², N-bromosaccharin (NBSA)³, N-chloronicotinimide (NCN)⁴ and N-bromophthalimide (NBP)⁵ have been used as oxidimetric titrants in the potentiometric determination of some typical reductants in aqueous acetic acid medium.

The new N-halo compound 1-chlorobenzimidazole (CBI), though has been used as a reagent in the oxidative reactions of aromatic aldehydes⁶, not been utilized hitherto as oxidimetric titrant for organic and inorganic reductants. In the present investigation the utility of CBI as an oxidimetric titrant has been documented in aqueous acetic acid medium.

Materials and methods :

1-Chlorobenzimidazole (CBI) was prepared by literature method⁷ and its purity was checked by iodometric titration. For analytical work fresh solutions of CBI were prepared in anhydrous acetic acid (E. Merck). Standard solutions of reductants were prepared in acetic acid-water medium using 2 N HCl (80% (v/v) acetic acid-water medium).

Potentiometric technique :

The oxidant solution was taken in a 100 mL beaker [0.1 g of CBI in 20 mL of glacial acetic acid (~0.03 mol dm⁻³)] in which a Platinum-Saturated Calomel Electrode assembly was set up. The reductant solution was taken in

a micro burette and was added to the titrant solution. The experimental solution was stirred automatically using magnetic stirrer and the change in emf was followed. Near the equivalence point CBI was restricted to 0.1 mL. The titrations were continued until there was no significant change in potential on further addition of the titrant.

The following 15 reductants were estimated using CBI in different concentrations : ascorbic acid, resorcinol, succinic acid, thiourea, iodide, beta naphthol, glucose, semicarbazide, anthranilic acid, phenol, FeSO₄, MnSO₄, aniline, acetanilide and benzoin.

Results and discussion

The results of potentiometric titrations of the 15 reductants are presented in the Table 1. In the potentiometric method, the equivalence points were calculated by the graphical method⁸ and the results were checked by the Hostetter-Roberts⁹ method and the Yan method¹⁰.

During the reaction CBI undergoes reduction to give benzimidazole as per the equation

[CBI : 1-Chlorobenzimidazole and BI : benzimidazole]

The formal redox potential of CBI/BI couple involved in the above reaction was found to be +1.08 V at 25 °C indicating that CBI is moderately strong oxidant. This is evidenced by the results and the sharp changes in potential observed at the equivalence points.

All the reductants undergo their usual oxidation scheme

Table 1

Sl. no.	Reductant	Range studied (mmol)	Standard deviation ^a	Average error (%)
1.	Ascorbic acid	0.08–0.25	0.42	±0.423
2.	Resorcinol	0.09–0.18	1.50	±0.634
3.	Succinic acid	0.10–0.20	0.70	±0.310
4.	Thiourea	0.10–0.25	0.55	±0.784
5.	Iodide (I ⁻)	0.09–0.23	0.50	±0.671
6.	Beta naphthol	0.20–0.44	0.51	±0.475
7.	Glucose	Unsuccessful	-	-
8.	Semicarbazide	0.10–0.30	0.89	±0.325
9.	Anthranilic acid	0.09–0.27	0.4	±0.444
10.	Phenol	0.17–0.39	0.71	±0.578
11.	FeSO ₄	0.06–0.15	0.95	±0.9375
12.	MnSO ₄	0.15–0.39	0.65	±0.560
13.	Acetanilide	0.20–0.51	0.55	±0.670
14.	Aniline	0.30–0.95	0.82	±0.430
15.	Benzoin	0.21–0.67	0.67	±0.350

^a8 replicates.

reported elsewhere¹. Thus ascorbic acid is oxidized to dehydroascorbic acid, succinic acid to maleic acid, thiourea to nitrogen, iodide to iodine, semicarbazide to semicarbazone, benzoin to benzoic acid, aniline, phenol, resorcinol, anthranilic acid, acetanilide and beta naphthol all get chlorinated under the experimental conditions. Fe^{II} and Mn^{II} are oxidized to +3 state.

In conformity with these oxidation schemes one equivalent of oxidant is consumed by one equivalent of Fe^{II}, Mn^{II}, iodide, 2 equivalents of ascorbic acid, benzoin, succinic acid, 4 equivalents of semicarbazide, thiourea, 6 equivalents of aniline, phenol, resorcinol, beta naphthol, anthranilic acid and acetanilide.

Conclusion :

The present study shows that CBI functions as an effective oxidizer for all these reductants and can be employed as an analytical reagent for a quite number of determinations.

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